

ISOLATION AND EVALUATION OF PROBIOTIC STRAINS FROM DAIRY PRODUCTS

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Abstract:

The present study aimed to isolate, identify and preliminarily characterize strains of *Lactobacillus* species, *Lactococcus* species, *Bifidobacterium* species, *Leuconostoc* species, *Streptococcus* species obtained from dairy products. Samples of raw milk, fermented milk, curd, yogurt, yakult, paneer, cheese and buttermilk were collected from local dairy sources, processed under aseptic conditions. The isolates were characterized based on colony, morphology, gram staining and biochemical tests such as catalyze reactions. Samples were serially diluted and cultured on selective media such as MRS Agar and Rogosa SL Agar under anaerobic or microaerophilic conditions at 37 c for 24 – 48 hours. The isolates were found to be gram-positive, non-spore forming and catalyze negative behavior indicating typical characteristics of *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Leuconostoc* species of dairy products. These finding confirm that dairy products are reliable natural sources of probiotic bacteria potential application in functional food development and human health improvement. The antagonistic properties of these isolates against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, were examined using agar well diffusion method. Low pH of fermented dairy products can reduce their survival rate. Temperature and storage time also affect bacterial count and activity

Keywords: Probiotic, Milk, Curd, Yakult, Paneer

Introduction:

Probiotic strains: These are specific type of live microorganisms that when administered in adequate amounts, provide health benefits to the host by improving /restoring its intestinal microbial balance. They are also called as “friendly bacteria” or “good bacteria”. Probiotic is a term derived from to Greek words “pro” and “biotic” which means “Promote life” or “for life”. In 2006 the World Health Organization (WHO) approved *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* species as good probiotics which are safe for human consumption. In recent decades, growing scientific and commercial interest in probiotics has been driven by increasing awareness of their role in maintaining gut health, enhancing immune function, and preventing or managing gastrointestinal disorders. Among the various sources of probiotics, fermented dairy products represent one of the most important and widely consumed vehicles for delivering beneficial microorganisms to humans.

Dairy products such as yogurt, cheese, fermented milk, Paneer and buttermilk provide an ideal environment for the growth and survival of probiotic bacteria due to their rich nutrient composition, buffering capacity and favourable PH. These products commonly harbour lactic acid bacteria (LAB) such as *Lactobacillus*, *Leuconostoc*, *Lactococcus*, and *Streptococcus*, as well as bifidobacteria (*Bifidobacterium* spp.), which are among the most extensively studied probiotic microorganisms. The regular consumption of probiotic-rich dairy products has been associated with improved digestion, modulation of intestinal microbiota, reduction of lactose intolerance symptoms, and protection against pathogenic microorganisms.

Diverse traditional dairy products with health-enhancing benefits, such as improvement of nutrient absorption, inactivation of toxins and anti-pathogenic activities, are used worldwide. According to scientific reports, antiallergic effect, anticancer effect, increasing fat loss, immune response of the host, improvement symptoms of IBS, intestinal inflammation, and antibiotic induced diarrhea are other useful effects of probiotics. Today, India is the largest producer of milk in the world and the Indian dairy industry is witnessing rapid changes. Curd is the most popular fermented dairy product in India, prepared by the use of mixed mesophilic cultures that ferment lactose to lactic acid. Products like yogurt are more known for therapeutic effects than nutritional value. Probiotics are microorganism's active factors, which show the beneficial impacts on the host health. Probiotics significantly affect the bioavailability of nutrients in the human body by facilitating the absorption of magnesium and calcium from milk proteins, digesting lactose and producing folate and B vitamins. *Lactobacillus* and *Enterococcus* species are common lactic acid bacteria (Gram-positive and non-toxic bacteria), which are usually consumed as probiotics. Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are generally recognized. *Lactobacilli* play an important role in controlling undesirable microflora in the gut and can be used as biological preservatives and are raised naturally in foods. *Bifidobacterium* species are crucial members of a healthy human gut microbiota. This bacterium protects against GIT infections, inflammation and metabolic diseases. *Bifidobacterium* species are oxygen-sensitive (anaerobic), so they may lose viability during processing and storage. A *Bifidobacterium* strain was 1st isolated by Henry Tissier from the faeces of breast-fed infants; he named the bacterium "Bacillus bifidus". *Leuconostoc* is a genus of gram positive, non-spore forming, facultatively anaerobic lactic acid bacteria (LAB). Isolation and characterization of probiotic bacteria from dairy products are essential steps in identifying novel strains with potential functional and therapeutic properties. Indigenous probiotic strains isolated from traditional or locally produced dairy foods may exhibit superior adaptability to specific environmental conditions and enhanced probiotic efficacy.

The isolation process typically involves selective enrichment and culturing techniques using specialized media, followed by phenotypic, biochemical, and molecular identification. Lactic acid bacteria and bifidobacteria often require specific growth conditions such as anaerobic or microaerophilic environments, selective agents, and optimized incubation temperatures. Accurate identification of isolated strains is crucial, as probiotic properties are highly strain-dependent and cannot be generalized at the species level alone.

In addition to isolation, the assessment of probiotic potential involves evaluating tolerance to acidic pH and bile salts, antimicrobial activity against pathogenic bacteria, and the ability to

adhere to intestinal epithelial cells. These characteristics are critical for ensuring the survival of probiotics during gastrointestinal transit and their functional interaction with the host. Consequently, research focusing on the isolation of probiotics from dairy products contributes to the development of functional foods and supports the selection of effective and safe probiotic strains for human consumption.

Scientific Classification of Probiotic Strains Present in the Dairy Products:

Lactobacillus

Domain: Bacteria

Phylum: Firmicutes (also known as Bacillota)

Class: Bacilli

Order: Lactobacillales

Family: Lactobacillaceae

Genus: Lactobacillus

Species: Several species found in dairy products such as *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *Lactobacillus kefir*, *Lactobacillus helveticus*, etc.

Bifidobacterium

Domain: Bacteria

Phylum: Actinobacteria

Class: Actinobacteria

Order: Bifidobacterial

Family: Bifidobacteriaceae

Genus: Bifidobacterium

Species: Species found in dairy products are *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium animalis*, *Bifidobacterium longum*.

BIFIDOBACTERIUM

Leuconostoc

Domain: Bacteria

Phylum: Firmicutes

Class: Bacilli

Order: Lactobacillales

Family: Leuconostocaceae

Genus: Leuconostoc

Species: Leuconostoc mesenteroids, Leuconostoc pseudomesenteriod

LEUCONOSTOC

Lactococcus

Domain: Bacteria

Phylum: Bacillota

Order: Lactobacillales

Family: Streptococcaceae

Genus: Lactococcus

Species: Lactococcus lactis, Lactococcus cremoris.

LACTOCOCCUS

Streptococcus

Domain: Bacteria

Phylum: Bacillota

Class: Bacilli

Order: Lactobacillales

Family: Streptococcaceae

Genus: Streptococcus

Species: Streptococcus thermophilus

STREPTOCOCCUS

Table: Probiotic Strains in Dairy Products and Their Uses

Probiotic Strain	Common Dairy Sources	Primary Uses/ Health Benefits
1.Lactobacillus acidophilus	Milk, yogurt, fermented milk	Enhances lactose digestion, improves gut flora, reduces diarrhea, boosts immunity.
2.Lactobacillus bulgaricus	Yogurt (starter)	Aids fermentation, supports digestion, reduces lactose tolerance.
3.Streptococcus thermophilus	Yogurt, fermented milk	Improves lactose metabolism, reduces inflammation, supports gut health.
4.Lactobacillus casei	Yogurt, cheese, probiotic drinks	Improves digestion, reduces constipation, enhances immune response.
5.Lactobacillus rhamnosus GG	Probiotic yogurt, dairy drinks	Strong evidence for reducing diarrhea, boosting immunity,

		improving gut integrity.
6.Lactobacillus plantarum	Curd, some cheeses, fermented milk	Anti-inflammatory, improves nutrient absorption, supports barrier.
7.Lactobacillus helveticus	Cheese, fermented milk	Reduces anxiety, supports calcium absorption, improves sleep quality.
8.Lactobacillus kefir	kefir	Controls pathogenic bacteria, enhances gut health, anti-inflammatory.
9.Bifidobacterium bifidum	Milk, yogurt, infant milk products	Enhances immunity, digestion, prevents constipation, protects gut lining.
10.Bifidobacterium longum	Fermented milk, probiotic drinks	Reduces IBS symptoms, supports gut-brain axis, improves bowel regularity.
11.Bifidobacterium animalis subsp. lactis	Yogurt, probiotic milk drinks	Improves stool frequency, boosts immune cells, reduces GI discomfort.
12.Leuconostoc mesenteroides	Buttermilk, curd, fermented cream	Produces dextrans, supports fermentation, mild probiotic effects, improves digestion.
13.Lactococcus lactis	Curd, buttermilk, cheese	Produces lactic acid, supports digestion, contributes to flavor and texture.
14.Saccharomyces kefir (yeast in kefir)	kefir	Enhances digestion, controls harmful microbes, antifungal effects.

Study Methodology:

Sample Collection

Sample collection is a critical initial step in the isolation of probiotic microorganisms from dairy products, as it directly influences the diversity, viability, and representativeness of the microbial population recovered. Proper selection, handling, transportation, and storage of dairy samples are essential to prevent contamination, microbial loss, or overgrowth of undesirable microorganisms. In the present study, careful attention was given to aseptic techniques and standardized procedures to ensure reliable and reproducible results.

Selection of Dairy Samples

A variety of dairy products were selected for analysis to ensure a broad representation of probiotic microflora. These included fermented dairy products such as yogurt, curd, fermented milk, cheese, and Yakult, which are known to be rich sources of lactic acid bacteria and bifidobacteria. Both commercially available and locally prepared dairy products were included in order to compare microbial diversity and to explore the presence of indigenous probiotic strains. Traditional dairy products, in particular, were considered valuable due to the absence of standardized starter cultures, allowing naturally occurring microorganisms to dominate the fermentation process.

The selection of samples was based on factors such as source of samples, freshness, collection at aseptic conditions. Products containing live cultures and minimal preservatives were prioritized, as preservatives may inhibit the growth of probiotic bacteria.

Importance of Sample Collection in Probiotic Isolation

Effective sample collection plays a pivotal role in the successful isolation of probiotic bacteria. Improper handling may result in loss of oxygen-sensitive organisms such as *Bifidobacterium*, while contamination may interfere with selective isolation of lactic acid bacteria and *Leuconostoc* species. By following standardized and aseptic collection methods, the probability of isolating viable and diverse probiotic strains is significantly enhanced.

Aseptic Collection Procedures

All dairy samples were collected aseptically to minimize the risk of external contamination. Sterile gloves, sterile containers and sterilized sampling tools were used throughout the collection process.

Liquid dairy products such as milk, yogurt, and buttermilk were transferred into sterile screw-capped bottles, while semi-solid and solid products such as curd and cheese were collected using sterile spatulas and placed into sterile containers.

Each container was properly labelled with essential information including sample type, source, date and time of collection, and sample code.

Labelling was performed immediately after collection to avoid sample mix-ups and ensure accurate traceability during laboratory analysis.

Transportation of Samples

Following collection, samples were transported to the laboratory under controlled conditions to preserve microbial viability.

Refrigerated conditions are crucial to slow down microbial metabolism and prevent the overgrowth of fast-growing non-target microorganisms that may outcompete probiotic bacteria.

Transportation time was kept to a minimum, and all samples were delivered to the laboratory within 4–6 hours of collection whenever possible. In cases where immediate processing was not feasible, samples were stored temporarily under refrigeration until further analysis.

Storage Prior to Processing

Upon arrival at the laboratory, samples were examined appropriately.

Samples were then stored at 4°C and processed within 24 hours to ensure maximum recovery of viable probiotic microorganisms. Prolonged storage was avoided, as extended refrigeration can reduce the viability of sensitive probiotic strains, particularly *Bifidobacterium* species, which are highly sensitive to oxygen and environmental stress.

Storage containers were kept tightly sealed to prevent moisture loss and contamination. Samples were handled in a biosafety cabinet whenever possible to maintain aseptic conditions.

Sample Preparation for Microbiological Analysis

Prior to microbial isolation, dairy samples were prepared under sterile conditions.

Liquid samples were mixed thoroughly by gentle shaking to ensure uniform distribution of microorganisms. Solid and semi-solid samples such as cheese and curd were weighed aseptically and homogenized using sterile mortars, blenders, or stomacher bags.

A known quantity of each sample (usually 1 g or 1 mL) was transferred into sterile diluent such as physiological saline or buffered peptone water.

Homogenization was performed to release microorganisms from the food matrix and to obtain a representative microbial suspension. This initial suspension served as the stock solution for subsequent serial dilutions.

ISOLATION PROCEDURE

Materials Required

- Dairy sample (curd / yogurt / fermented milk)
- Sterile test tubes
- Sterile pipettes
- Physiological saline or peptone water
- MRS agar plates
- Anaerobic jar or candle jar
- Incubator
- Inoculating loop

- Microscope
- Gram staining reagents
- Hydrogen peroxide (for catalase test)

Procedure

1. Collect the dairy sample aseptically in a sterile container.
2. Transfer 1 g or 1 mL of the sample into 9 mL of sterile saline or peptone water and mix thoroughly.
3. Prepare serial dilutions of the sample suspension.
4. Inoculate appropriate dilutions onto MRS agar plates using the spread plate technique.
5. Incubate the plates at 30–37°C for 24–48 hours under anaerobic or microaerophilic conditions.
6. Observe the plates for characteristic probiotic colonies.
7. Pick well-isolated colonies and subculture them on fresh MRS agar to obtain pure cultures.
8. Perform Gram staining and catalase test for preliminary identification.

Observation

- Colonies appeared small, circular, creamy-white on MRS agar.
- Microscopic observation showed Gram-positive rods or cocci.
- Catalase test was negative.

Result

Probiotic bacteria were successfully isolated from the dairy sample and preliminarily identified as lactic acid bacteria.

Precautions

- Maintain strict aseptic conditions throughout the experiment.
 - Use sterile media and instruments.
 - Avoid prolonged exposure of samples to air.
 - Incubate under appropriate conditions.
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Precautions and Quality Control

Strict aseptic techniques were maintained throughout the sample collection and preparation process. All glassware and equipment were sterilized prior to use, and work surfaces were disinfected regularly. Personnel involved in sample handling followed standard laboratory safety practices to prevent contamination and ensure data reliability.

Quality control measures included the use of blank controls to monitor contamination and repeated sampling where necessary to confirm reproducibility. Proper documentation of sample handling procedures was maintained to ensure traceability and compliance with laboratory standards.

Data Analysis:

Data from the laboratory were stored and transferred into Microsoft Excel 2016 Spreadsheet analyzed using STATA version 13.

Evaluation of Probiotic Activity:

1.Bile Tolerance Test:

The isolated strains were grown in MRS broth containing 0.2% of bile salt for 24-36 h under anaerobic conditions at 37°C. Culture broths with turbidity more than 0.5 units at 600 nm were classified as bile tolerant strains. These strains were further grown in MRS broth containing higher concentrations of 0.5 and 1.0% (w/v) of bile salt to assay their survival rate. The survival rate was expressed as the percentage of viable cells in the presence of bile salt compared to that without bile salt.

OBSERVATION:

The growth in 0.2% bile salts are as follows

Yogurt isolate showed excellent growth in the presence of bile salts.

Curd isolate showed good growth in the presence of bile salts.

Milk isolate showed moderate growth in the presence of bile salts.

Paneer isolate showed reduced growth in the presence of bile salts.

INFERENCE:

S.NO:	SAMPLE SOURCE	GROWTH IN 0.2' % BILE	INTERPRETATION
1	Yogurt	High	Highly tolerant
2	Curd	Good	Good tolerant
3	Milk	Moderate	Moderately tolerant

4	Paneer	Poor	Poorly tolerant
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2. Acid Tolerance Test:

The isolated strains were grown in MRS broth tubes at different pH ranges, i.e. pH 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 and incubated at 37°C for 48 - 72 hrs. From each tube 0.1 ml of inoculated culture was poured into MRS agar medium by using pour plate method and incubated at 37°C for 48 hrs. The growth of different culture on MRS agar media was examined to measure the pH tolerance of the isolated culture. Isolates which were growing on the agar were considered to be acid tolerant strain.

3. NaCl Tolerance Test:

NaCl tolerance of isolated Lactobacillus strains was determined by using MRS broth with different NaCl concentrations (1 - 10%) and incubated at 37°C for 24-36 hours. After incubation 0.1 ml of culture from each tube was used to grow in agar medium by pour plate method. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and observed for comparative growth in these plates.

4. Temperature Sensitivity:

The selected *Lactobacillus* strains were inoculated into different MRS broth tubes and incubated at different temperatures, i.e. 25, 30, 37, 40 and 45°C for 48 hours. By using pour plate method the isolates then cultured on agar medium. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and observed for comparative growth in these plates.

5. Sugar Fermentation Test:

The selected *Lactobacillus* strains were evaluated for fermentation of different carbohydrates and sugar alcohols. Different carbohydrates and sugar alcohols used in this fermentation tests were arabinose, glucose, fructose, galactose, sucrose, lactose, starch and mannitol. The test organisms were inoculated into a broth containing the test sugar and incubated at 37°C for 48 to 96 hours. A bright yellow color indicates the production of enough acid products from fermentation of the sugar to drop the pH to 6.9 or less. Gas production was investigated with a Durham tube, a small inverted vial filled with the carbohydrate fermentation broth. Yellow color or yellow color with gas bubble was considered as positive result and red color with no gas bubble was considered as negative result.

OBSERVATION:

Yogurt isolate showed rapid and intense fermentation with prominent acid production, confirming efficient carbohydrate metabolism.

Curd isolate showed strong acid production with complete colour change, indicating positive sugar fermentation test.

Milk isolate showed acid production indicated by complete colour change.

Paneer isolate showed weak fermentation.

RESULT:

S.NO	SAMPLE SOURCE	COLOUR CHANGE	GAS FORMATION	FERMENTATION RESULT
1	Yogurt	Red to Yellow	Absent	Strongly positive
2	Curd	Red to Yellow	Absent	Strongly positive
3	Milk	Red to Yellow	Absent	Moderately positive
4	Paneer	Red to Yellow	Absent	Positive

Sugar fermentation test

- Glucose test
- Maltose test
- Sucrose test
- Lactose test
- Some will appear with gas production

6. Antimicrobial Activity:

Strains are tested for their ability to inhibit pathogens like *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *Salmonella* using agar well diffusion method. In this method, agar plates are inoculated with a standardized inoculum of the test microorganism. Then, filter paper discs about 6mm in diameter containing the test compound at a desired concentration, are placed on the agar surface. The Petri dishes are incubated under suitable conditions. Generally, antimicrobial agent diffuses into the agar and inhibits germination and growth of the test microorganism and then the diameters of inhibition growth zones are measured.

7. Biochemical tests:

Probiotic microorganisms such as Lactobacillus, Bifidobacterium, Lactococcus, and Streptococcus are identified and characterized using various biochemical tests. These tests help in confirming their morphology, enzymatic activity, and metabolic nature.

A. Gram staining

Principle:

Gram staining differentiates bacteria based on the composition of their cell wall. Gram-positive bacteria retain the crystal violet–iodine complex and appear purple, whereas Gram-negative bacteria lose the stain and appear pink.

Procedure:

Prepare a thin smear of the bacterial culture on a clean glass slide.

Heat-fix the smear gently.

Flood the slide with crystal violet for 1 minute and rinse with water.

Add Gram's iodine for 1 minute and wash.

Decolorize with alcohol or acetone for a few seconds.

Counterstain with safranin for 30 seconds and rinse.

Observe under oil immersion (100×) microscope.

Result:

Most probiotic bacteria appear Gram-positive (purple) rods or cocci.

Inference:

Confirms Gram-positive nature of probiotic strains.

B. Catalase Test:

Principle:

The catalase enzyme breaks down hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen, producing bubbles. Most probiotic bacteria lack catalase enzyme.

Procedure:

Place a drop of 3% hydrogen peroxide on a clean glass slide.

Using a sterile loop, transfer a small amount of bacterial culture onto the drop.

Observe for immediate bubble formation.

Result:

No bubbles → Catalase negative

Bubble formation → Catalase positive

Inference:

Probiotic bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* and *Streptococcus* are catalase negative.

C.Oxidase Test:

Principle:

The oxidase test detects the presence of cytochrome c oxidase enzyme, which is involved in aerobic respiration.

Procedure:

Place a few drops of oxidase reagent on filter paper.

Using a sterile wooden stick, smear the bacterial culture onto the reagent.

Observe color change within 10–30 seconds.

Result:

No color change → Oxidase negative

Dark purple/blue color → Oxidase positive

Inference:

Most probiotic bacteria are oxidase negative, indicating fermentative metabolism.

APPLICATIONS:

Isolated probiotic strains are cultured, harvested, and formulated into food or pharmaceutical products. They are administered orally in adequate viable counts to improve gut health, inhibit pathogens, and enhance immunity.

Probiotic strains isolated from dairy products such as yogurt, cheese, and fermented milk mainly belong to **Lactobacillus**, **Bifidobacterium**, **Lactococcus**, and **Streptococcus** species. These isolated strains have several important applications in food, health, and biotechnology.

1. Application in Functional Foods

Isolated probiotic strains are widely used in the production of functional dairy foods like yogurt, cheese, kefir, and fermented milk products. These probiotics improve the nutritional value, taste, and shelf life of food while providing health benefits such as better digestion and improved gut health.

2. Application in Human Health

Probiotic strains from dairy products help maintain a healthy balance of intestinal microflora. They are effective in preventing diarrhoea, reducing lactose intolerance, improving immunity, and lowering cholesterol levels. Some strains also help in managing gastrointestinal disorders such as irritable bowel syndrome (IBS).

3. Application in Pharmaceutical and Nutraceutical Products

After isolation and safety evaluation, probiotic strains are formulated into capsules, tablets, and sachets. These products are used as dietary supplements to promote digestive health and enhance immune response.

4. Application in Food Preservation

Certain isolated probiotic strains produce antimicrobial substances like organic acids and bacteriocins. These compounds inhibit the growth of harmful microorganisms and are used as natural preservatives to increase the shelf life and safety of food products.

5. Application as Starter Cultures

Probiotic strains isolated from dairy products are used as starter and adjunct cultures in fermentation. They help in flavour development, texture improvement, and consistency of dairy products such as cheese and yogurt.

6. Application in Animal Nutrition

Dairy-derived probiotics are used in animal feed as alternatives to antibiotics. They improve gut health, enhance growth performance, and increase disease resistance in poultry, cattle, and aquaculture.

7. Application in Biotechnology and Research

Isolated probiotic strains are used in research to study gut microbiota interactions and in biotechnology for the production of enzymes, vitamins, and bioactive compounds.

CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully demonstrated that dairy products are a rich and reliable source of probiotic microorganisms. Through systematic isolation and characterization, several bacterial strains with desirable probiotic properties were obtained. The isolated strains exhibited typical morphological and biochemical characteristics of lactic acid bacteria, confirming their probiotic potential.

Evaluation of the isolates revealed that they possessed key functional attributes required for probiotic application, including tolerance to acidic pH and bile salts, antimicrobial activity against selected pathogenic microorganisms, and satisfactory growth characteristics. These properties indicate their ability to survive gastrointestinal conditions and contribute to host health. Additionally, the use of commonly consumed dairy products highlights their importance as effective carriers for probiotic bacteria.

Overall, the findings support the potential use of isolated probiotic strains from dairy products in the development of functional foods and nutraceuticals. Further studies involving molecular identification, safety assessment, and in vivo evaluation are recommended to confirm their efficacy and suitability for commercial and therapeutic applications.

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